

Name	Position	Years of experience with Javascript	Years of experience in unit test with Javascript
P1	FullStack Developer	3 ~ 4 years	1 ~ 2 years
P2	FullStack Developer	5 ~ 10 years	5 ~ 10 years
P3	Backend Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P4	FullStack Developer	5 ~ 10 years	3 ~ 4 years
P5	Backend Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P6	QA Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P7	FullStack Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P8	FullStack Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P9	FullStack Developer	3 ~ 4 years	3 ~ 4 years
P10	Tech Lead	5 ~ 10 years	5 ~ 10 years
P11	FullStack Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P12	QA Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P13	FullStack Developer	5 ~ 10 years	3 ~ 4 years
P14	Technical Account Manager	5 ~ 10 years	5 ~ 10 years
P15	Backend Developer	5 ~ 10 years	1 ~ 2 years
P16	FullStack Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P17	Backend Developer	1 ~ 2 years	1 ~ 2 years
P18	Desenvolvedor Frontend	5 ~ 10 years	3 ~ 4 years
P19	Tech Lead	5 ~ 10 years	3 ~ 4 years
P20	FullStack Developer	5 ~ 10 years	1 ~ 2 years